

Transformation of international and regional labor and employment markets under the influence of digital platforms

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Abstract— The article considers the specifics of regional and international labor markets and their transformation under the influence of digitalization as a dominant trend in the modern market economy. The main positive and negative impacts of digitalization on employment are characterized. The economic essence of digital labor platforms and platform-based employment as a new form of employee-employer relationships is explored. Barriers that reduce the effectiveness of the establishment and development of platform-based employment are identified, and key directions for its improvement are proposed. Their practical implementation leads to an increase in the population's digital skills, a rise in the number of qualified personnel in the digitalization of the labor market, and the reduction of regional disparities in Internet accessibility across different areas.

Keywords— Digital labor platforms, labor market, employment, freelancing, digital technologies.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the Russian economy, the labor market is viewed as a dominant sector. Its formation began with the country's gradual transition from a planned economy to a market-oriented one. Currently, it is supported by an institutional framework structured as a hierarchical national-regional system of formal norms and values-based orientations.

According to many researchers, the labor and employment market changes due to external environmental factors that are catalysts for internal radical modernization [1, 2].

Currently, a key trend in the development of the Russian socio-economic system is digitalization. This directly impacts the nature of labor relations and the state of the labor market.

The impact of digitalization on international and regional labor markets has only recently become the subject of scientific research, though still limited in scope. These studies address the replacement of human labor with digital technologies, digital workforce mobility, the functioning of digital offices, and the characteristics of digital labor platforms. The latter is the least developed area due to insufficient empirical experience, the ambiguous understanding of digital labor platforms, and their insufficient institutional support. Moreover, platform-based employment has positive and negative consequences for the modern labor market, necessitating the development of regulatory measures to minimize its adverse effects on the dynamics of labor relations.

In this context, the article aims to substantiate the key strategies for mitigating the negative impact of digital labor platforms on the development trends of international and regional labor markets. This is achieved through the systematic analysis and examination of the transformational processes occurring in this field.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In forming the main provisions of this article, we referred to publications on digital platforms (including labor-oriented) and their impact on the transformation of international and regional labor markets posted in the Scopus and Web of Science scientific databases. Professional publications published in these journals over the past five years were accepted for consideration.

We searched for the necessary materials and systematically studied them using the following keywords: digital labor platforms, labor market, informal employment, freelancing, self-employment, platform employment, and digital technologies.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the course of this research, several scientific propositions were formulated regarding the transformation of international and regional labor markets and employment under the influence of digital platforms. The concept of digital labor platforms was clarified, and their types were systematized. The key transformation directions in international and regional labor markets and employment due to the impact of digital labor platforms were identified, and measures were developed to minimize their negative effects on employment.

The labor market in all its forms, including international and regional, evolves along trajectories shaped by a system of interrelated factors, each with its specific content (economic, technical-technological, demographic, and natural-environmental, i.e., ecological). The most significant outcome of the unidirectional influence of these factors is the alteration in labor market demand and supply, the emergence of new significant qualities in labor resources, the generation of new forms of employment, and the fundamental modernization of labor-related business processes.

Today, digitalization is the dominant factor driving new trends in the labor market [3, 4].

In a conceptual sense, the term “digitalization” can be interpreted as the integration of digital technologies, data transmission channels, and digital transmission devices into all segments of socio-economic life across various classifications. This concept is also associated with the new techno-technological paradigm known as Industry 4.0, which represents an innovative restructuring of the entire value chain at all stages of the product or service lifecycle based on automation and data exchange.

Digitalization is a dominant trend that directly impacts the labor market across all its parameters in various countries and regions. The main directions of labor market transformation under the influence of digitalization are shown in Figure 1.

Thus, the concept of the digital economy is complex and multifaceted, lacking a unified interpretation and evolving in line with the socio-economic development of regions.

One of the most significant directions in the transformation of the labor market under the influence of digitalization is the emergence of new forms of employment that differ significantly from traditional models. A form of employment is understood as the organizational and legal methods or conditions of labor utilization.

In 2015, the European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions prepared a report in which scholars presented new forms of employment (Figure 2) [5].

Fig. 2 New forms of employment as interpreted by the European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions

Given the creative and unconventional nature of new forms of employment, digital platform-based employment stands out as the most significant among them, having emerged as a response to the global recession and lacking any previous analogs. The digital transformation of business processes has led to the development of a creative form of employment utilizing digital platforms.

The study of digital platforms by Russian economists is still in its formative stage, and the number of publications on this topic remains limited [6]. Nevertheless, both academic and practical communities have come to understand these platforms as multi-sided and hybrid structures aimed at creating value through the facilitation of direct interactions and transactions between groups of external users.

The number of digital platforms is growing rapidly. Currently, the following types can be identified (Table 1) [7].

TABLE I
TYPES OF DIGITAL PLATFORMS

Digital platform type	Characteristics
Marketplaces	Platforms where sellers and buyers find each other and interact
Classifieds	Platforms designed for posting advertisements for the sale or purchase of goods and services
Sharing platforms	Platforms for the collective use and consumption of goods and services, as well as rental platforms
Labor market platforms (digital labor platforms)	Platforms that act as intermediaries between suppliers and consumers
Fintech solutions and crowdfunding	Platforms for attracting and managing financial resources using digital technologies
Information reference platforms	Platforms intended for obtaining reference information
Entertainment resources	Platforms designed to provide access to entertainment
Social networks	Platforms that allow users to communicate and interact

As for digital labor platforms, the most comprehensive definition was formulated by A.V. Shevchuk. According to A.V. Shevchuk, digital labor platforms are a type of information system whose regulatory function is the technological and industrial coordination of business processes, wherein workers and clients interact regarding the purchase and sale of services. These systems are characterized by their episodic nature, focusing on local labor tasks and short-term projects [8].

There are few examples of digital labor platforms (including HR, Profi, and Freelance). However, their number is continuously growing as they facilitate employment and serve as a link in labor relations. According to the Institute for Social Policy, 14.7% of Russians aged 18-24 have had some experience with platform-based employment, with one in ten using platforms to find temporary work and about 2% having experience with platform-based employment as their primary source of income. Research results indicate that the number of people employed in the platform economy totals 15.5 million, with 1.7 million having temporary employment through such platforms [9].

Platform-based employment has become widespread among the youth as evidenced by the following data. The age distribution of workers engaged in platform-based employment is as follows: 37.5% are aged 30 to 39; 25% are aged 40-49; about 20% are aged 20 to 29; and 3% are aged 60 to 69 [10].

The advantages of platform-based employment are evident, particularly in regional labor markets, as they address pressing issues faced by the Russian regions:

- Provides opportunities for quick employment for individuals temporarily out of work due to the bankruptcy of regional enterprises, particularly those that are budget- or city-forming;
- Allows young people, especially students in various forms of education, to obtain temporary employment to supplement their scholarships with additional income;
- Enhances opportunities for residents of municipal areas in the region to engage in individual entrepreneurship and self-employment, which are currently primary forms of platform-based employment;
- Enables residents of regions to earn extra income, which is particularly important amid inflationary processes and declining real incomes among many Russian citizens;
- Significantly simplifies the process for job seekers to enter the labor market and broadens the scope for job searches in alignment with their motivation and skill levels;
- Lowers transaction costs for both job seekers and employers;
- Enhances the interaction between labor market supply and demand and minimizes structural unemployment;
- Contributes to a decrease in the informal sector within the regional economy.

The digitalization of the labor market results in positive and negative trends, including those related to platform-based employment. The following barriers can be identified that reduce the effectiveness of the establishment and development of platform-based employment (Figure 3).

Fig. 3 Barriers that reduce the effectiveness of the formation and development of platform employment in the Russian regions

Labor platforms are divided into two groups: local and global. On local platforms, work is performed at specific locations (e.g., food delivery and taxi services). Workers on such platforms typically have standardized uniforms and vehicles. On global labor platforms, work is carried out remotely (e.g., translation and text writing). The primary goal of these platforms is to facilitate interaction between users.

Currently, platform-based employment is not specifically regulated by the Russian law. In this context, the issue of adopting a separate law on platform-based employment is highly relevant. Such a law could address the following important provisions:

- The mandatory maintenance of a register of digital platforms;
- The obligation of digital platforms to form and provide a rating of performers;
- The introduction of a requirement for the mandatory payment of wages to employees of digital labor platforms and their voluntary social insurance;
- The possibility of creating an association of citizens employed by the platform in the form of a trade union;
- The introduction of a clear procedure for resolving disputes between digital labor platforms and the workers employed on them.

The growth of platform-based employment requires potential workers to have a relatively high level of digital skills and competencies necessary for online work. Currently, Russia lags in this area, which is one of the main barriers to improving the efficiency of platform employment.

Without improving digital literacy, transforming the labor market in any direction is impossible. This is a fact that hardly needs further proof. In most cases, residents of municipalities take it upon themselves to acquire digital competencies often with the help of government support through grants, free training, and

targeted programs. To work on digital labor platforms, potential workers need at least basic skills, such as searching for and analyzing information online, using media tools and technical devices, and communicating with different participants on social networks. These skills are crucial for socially vulnerable groups, such as people with disabilities, single mothers, retirees, and the unemployed. For them, platform-based employment could provide much-needed additional income, especially in the face of rising prices for goods and services.

In this context, the primary focus for improving digital literacy among the population is expanding the types of government support. A notable example is the adoption of the professional standard “Consultant in the Field of Digital Literacy Development (Digital Curator)” approved by the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Russian Federation on October 31, 2018. The main role of a digital curator is to assist in developing digital literacy across various aspects of people’s lives. The digital curator is a new profession that has only recently emerged and has yet to become widespread in Russia, despite the pressing need for such a role.

In addition to improving digital literacy among the population, it is also crucial to significantly increase the number of specialists focused on the digital transformation of the labor market. The National Program “Digital Economy of the Russian Federation” offers significant opportunities, particularly through the “Workforce for the Digital Economy” project. In 2022, the Ministry of Digital Development, Communications, and Mass Media of the Russian Federation expanded the National Program to include three additional projects, one dedicated to developing the human resources potential of the IT industry.

Several factors influence the shortage of investment in digital technology development:

- Economic uncertainty;
- Lack of sufficient working capital;
- Investment risks;
- High interest rates on commercial loans.

To attract additional investments for the digitalization of the labor market, it is essential to leverage government support, secure funding from venture capital funds, and employ effective mechanisms for collaboration between private businesses and the public sector represented by the state.

The analysis of the current issues in the Russian labor market shows that the standard of living, as measured by the Human Development Index, significantly impacts its market transformation, including platform-based employment. The country’s regions vary widely in their socio-economic development, with some regions lagging and others being considered depressed areas that still lack a clear development strategy, particularly in the digital transformation of key industries, sectors, and labor markets. In these regions, strategic development plans must include a dedicated section focused on establishing a digital economy. Local governments, regional employment centers, and corporate social responsibility initiatives should play a leading role in this process.

The uneven development of the Russian regions within the country’s spatial framework leads to digital inequality, most evident in the varying levels of Internet access among the population. Therefore, a strategic goal for the socio-economic development of the national economy is to ensure equal access to Internet services for all citizens.

Addressing this complex and financially demanding issue is particularly important for rural areas, and this must be considered when developing local programs and plans for their growth.

Thus, the dominant direction in modernizing regional and international markets characterized by the emergence and development of platform-based employment faces barriers. Overcoming these barriers requires the combined efforts of all market participants, including public authorities. In this context, public-private and municipal-private partnerships are appropriate and justified as they offer a way to optimize the funding sources for platform employment initiatives.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A key effective mechanism of a market economy that ensures the sustainable socio-economic development of Russian society and impacts the quality of life of its population is the labor market. It represents a system of economic relations concerning the buying and selling of labor, i.e., the hiring and offering of the workforce.

Within the broader system of markets, regional and international labor markets hold a special place. The regional labor market is viewed as an economic category that determines a hierarchical socio-economic system based on the mechanisms of supply and demand, with such key factors as territorial isolation and regional business activity playing a decisive role. In contrast, the international labor market as one of the most important components of the global economy is built on commercial exchange, trade, and monetary relations between countries concerning the demand for and supply of labor of various qualifications.

Labor markets are influenced by numerous internal and external factors, characterized by a high level of turbulence. Within existing globalization and integration processes, the dominant factor driving the development of labor markets is their digital transformation. This transformation entails the integration of digital technologies, data transmission flows, and digital transmission devices into the structural elements of the labor market.

The impact of digitalization on the labor market is most evident in the emergence of new forms of employment. Platform-based employment is characterized by creativity and is regarded as the most prominent type. Within the broad category of digital platforms, digital labor platforms stand out as intermediaries between service providers and consumers.

The impact of digital labor platforms on employment has both positive and negative aspects. On the positive side, these platforms enable quick job placement, expand opportunities for entrepreneurship and self-employment, provide additional income for the region's population, reduce transaction costs for both job seekers and employers, match supply and demand in the labor market, and decrease informal employment in the regional economy. However, there are also negative effects, such as the reduction of traditional jobs, the disappearance of certain professions, increased risks for workers, a rise in structural unemployment, and a diminished role of collective labor relations.

It is essential to address several key barriers to enhance the effectiveness of regional and international labor markets through digital labor platforms. These include the lack of specialized legislation on platform-based employment, the low level of digital skills among the population, insufficient investment in digital technology, declining household incomes (which hinders the purchase of information goods), uneven access to the Internet in different regions, and a shortage of qualified professionals in platform employment.

Solving these problems will create a multiplier effect, amplifying the positive impact of labor market transformation on employment at regional and international levels and strengthening the benefits of digitalization for the workforce.

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